

Artificial Intelligence in Nigeria Health Sector

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Abstract

As the healthcare sector continues to experience the surge of innovative approaches to healthcare, artificial intelligence (AI) is taking the lead among medical service providers. The reason is obvious as AI tends to incorporate a number of algorithms to solve a given problem in the shortest time possible. In this study, AI in Nigeria healthcare sector was investigated. The review identified some ethical concerns in the use of AI in the healthcare sector as well as some areas of medical applications of AI in Nigeria. These areas include diseases diagnosis; drug discovery and development; personalized medicine; disease outbreak prediction among others. Results reveal that AI could revolutionize the healthcare sector in Nigeria if adequate measures are put in place. Based on these findings, the study recommends that stakeholders should establish a strategy that would allow the integration of AI into healthcare to be undertaken in a structured manner, complementing national health policy and standards. Furthermore, the place of investing in AI infrastructure and training programs are urgent.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Health, Sector.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems are programs that when confronted with a problem, either interpret machine learning, search relevant data, apply prior knowledge, make a decision based on information gleaned from these, or process information obtained in this manner through supervised or unsupervised learning before arriving at the best course of action [1-2]. AI can either use symbolic rules or learn a numeric model, and it can also adapt by analysing how the environment reacts to its past actions [3].

According to [4], artificial intelligence is a scientific discipline includes several approaches and techniques, such as machine learning (of which deep learning and reinforcement learning are specific examples), machine reasoning (which includes planning, scheduling, knowledge representation, and reasoning,

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search, and optimization), and robotics which provides control, perception, sensors, and actuators, as well as the integration of all other techniques into cyber-physical systems.

In a world where the vision of human development and global growth will be realized through digital technology, the use of digital technology, such as AI, will enable Africa (with over a billion people) to overcome health problems, especially with regard to the rise in infectious and non-communicable illnesses, maternity and child health, as well as other related issues [5-6]. For instance, Nigeria, home to the world's most vibrant youths, comprises more than half of West Africa's population of 250 million and is a major regional economic powerhouse in Africa [7]. The country is a regional economic powerhouse with huge human and natural assets, but innovation is slow because of reasons ranging from lack of adequate knowledge of AI to infrastructure issues, and lack of access to data [3]. Nigeria ranks 138 globally and 20 in the region in the Oxford Insight Government AI Readiness compared to South Africa, Kenya, and Ghana. The National Center for Artificial Intelligence and Robotics (NCAIR), established as a digital innovation office of the government, was to conduct research on and further understand the application and use of emerging technologies such as AI, Deep Learning, Extended Reality (XR-VR/MR/AR), Robotics and Drones, and the Internet of Things (IoT) [8].

The use of AI in healthcare in Nigeria is still nascent and still evolving. The use of AI in healthcare will improve the standard of healthcare provided to Nigerians [5]. It will also have several benefits such as improved laboratory workflow automation, precision diagnosis, personalized treatment plans, effective healthcare operations, early disease detection and prevention, drug discovery, and clinical research [9]. The application of AI in the medical field promises many advantages but the adoption of AI in the practice of medicine is mostly by the developed nations. Thus, the rollout of AI in Nigeria largely depends on the level of readiness and acceptability of doctors and the public about the technology [3]. In the light of these assertions, AI in Nigeria health sector is assessed in this study.

Ethical Concerns in the Use of AI in Healthcare

The use of AI in healthcare has a lot of ethical, moral, and social implications. Some of the legal challenges include issues around regulation, accountability for decisions, bias, data privacy regulations, and intellectual property rights [2]. It was revealed by [4] that there are no African regulations or other regulations anywhere in the world that specify responsibilities for adverse consequences that may occur as a result of using AI in healthcare, which is probable given the ways or places in which AI may be used in healthcare. The most likely answer will be the application of current laws, but many situations and locations are not anticipated by current laws and that is where current laws will impact patients and users. In many African countries, this will have legal effects on patients and users [6,9].

Some Healthcare Providers using AI

In Nigeria, there is XOLANI HEALTH, an AI and cloud solution for clinical decision-making. This includes software such as 'DICOM-X', a system to support image diagnosis and analysis, as well as 'Xolani AIR' which allows users to take a picture of a patient's body part and store data for future reference. There is the 'Xolani AIR', which involves features such as medical image analysis, abnormality detection, disease diagnosis, reporting, and so on. There is also ARONE, an App-based ordering system to procure medicines online. It's a platform that uses medical smart aerial logistics technology with AI and autonomous flight navigation software to run drones for the delivery of medical supplies between clinics, hospitals, laboratories, and health facilities.

Pronov is a provider of a telehealth platform that delivers clinical decision support. The company offers an AI-based platform that provides electronic medical records, diagnostic testing, prescriptions, education, referrals, chronic disease management, and other services. 10mg is an AI-powered logistics management system for the pharmaceutical ecosystem. The company's solution utilizes an AI algorithm based on the code tree model to match medical providers with financing partners to enable bulk medication purchases for pain management.

Hub Care Health is a Provider of an AI-enabled digital platform to provide healthcare services in person and online. Patients can book a tele-consultation, lab tests, vaccination, and prescribed medicines at home. Healthcare providers can join as a channel partner on the platform to manage patients remotely. Users can track and monitor the symptoms of the disease.

The applications of Artificial Intelligence in Nigeria healthcare sector

Artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to revolutionized healthcare in Nigeria. By applying AI technologies, many challenges in the healthcare sector can be tackled, and healthcare services can be improved in terms of quality, accessibility, and efficiency [7].

1. **Disease Diagnosis and Treatment:** AI can help to diagnose diseases by analysing medical images such as X-rays and MRIs, lab results and patient history. It can pick up subtle patterns and anomalies that humans might miss, helping to diagnose ailments earlier and more reliably [1].
2. **Telemedicine and Remote Consultations:** telemedicine platforms that use AI, people in rural areas and the developing world can access doctors via long-distance communications. AI, too, can 'see' the patient, helping to triage them, answer basic health queries and even suggest a diagnosis based on symptoms provided by the patient [5].
3. **Predictive Analytics and Disease Outbreak Prediction:** Thus, by processing vast amounts of data, AI would be able to detect signs of disease outbreaks, trace transmission of infectious diseases, and enable health authorities to prepare more effectively to head off a health emergency before it occurs [9].
4. **Personalised Medicine:** AI can analyse data from genetic factors, lifestyle assessments, and other sources and suggest personalized treatments that correlate with better outcomes and fewer side effects for an individual [3].
5. **Healthcare Administration and Operations:** AI can optimise administrative tasks such as scheduling, billing, and resource management, which in turn facilitates cost savings and an increase in efficiency across healthcare facilities [6].
6. **Drug Discovery and Development:** AI tools can help to screen biological data to identify targets that are likely to interact positively with a given compound, greatly accelerating the drug-discovery process and potentially bringing new drugs to market much more quickly and cheaply [1].
7. **Health Monitoring and Wearable Devices:** Patient health metrics, including vital signs, could be continuously recorded by wearable devices with sensors and analysed by artificial intelligence (AI) programs. Early warning signs of health problems could then be identified and addressed, and chronic conditions monitored on an ongoing basis [7].
8. **Mental Health Support:** AI in mental health applications could include giving advice and therapy using a chatbot or a virtual assistant. Chatbots may monitor patients' mental health status and alert them if it deteriorates [4].

9. Training and Education: AI can improve medical education and training, for example, with simulations, VR and adaptive learning environments through which medical students and professionals can develop new skills and stay up to date with the latest advances in medicine [2].

Conclusion

This review explains how artificial intelligence can be applied to the healthcare sector in Nigeria. Findings reveal that AI is likely to bring a revolution to the healthcare sector in Nigeria, providing new opportunities for efficiency, accuracy and accessibility. Nevertheless, Nigeria must overcome several obstacles, such as inadequate infrastructure, privacy issues, and lack of training, if it is to benefit from AI applications. For AI to be successfully implemented in Nigeria, the government must display the necessary political will. Also, the implementation of AI in Africa should be commercial-based. Furthermore, results show that AI holds the potential to revolutionized patient outcomes and care. It has the potential to revolutionized the quality of clinical laboratory testing and illness detection by being more precise, effective and economical. It can be used for population health management as well as in guideline development by optimizing pharmaceutical choices and providing accurate information in real-time. In general, all country users of health services can benefit in terms of improved turn-around time, broader access to treatment services via telehealth systems and lower cost of service delivery. Based on these results, the study recommends among others that the government must develop and implement a national AI strategy for healthcare. A defined strategy would allow the integration of AI into healthcare to be undertaken in a structured manner, complementing national health policy and standards. In addition, there is a need to invest in AI infrastructure and training programs. This infrastructure and training will help healthcare institutions and workers use AI technologies. Healthcare workers should also be engaged in continuous professional development to understand and leverage AI tools. They should collaborate with AI specialists to develop and refine AI tools. Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and Civil Societies should support AI-based healthcare projects and initiatives. Overall, healthcare organizations should integrate AI tools into clinical workflows to enhance patient care. These would enhance diagnostic accuracy, improve treatment planning, and facilitate patient monitoring, all of which contribute to better health outcomes.

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